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DESIGNING UNIFORMS WITH SPECIFIED PROPERTIES FOR FEMALE MILITARY FOR VARIOUS CONDITIONS

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Annotation: This article examines the improvement of methods for designing and evaluating the ergonomic rationality of special-purpose clothing designs with their practical development and implementation when creating new models of insulated field clothing for female military.

Keywords: Clothing, ergonomic quality, dynamic, kit, design, methodical approach, efficiency, goniometry, temperature.

TURLI XIL SHAROITLAR UCHUN HARBIY AYOLLAR UCHUN BELGILANGAN XUSUSIYATLARGA EGA FORMA DIZAYNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada harbiy xizmatchilar uchun izolyatsiya qilingan dala kiyimlarining yangi namunalarini yaratishda ularni amaliy ishlab chiqish va amalga oshirish bilan maxsus kiyim dizaynlarining ergonomik ratsionalligini loyihalash va baholash usullarini takomillashtirish ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kiyim, ergonomik sifat, dinamik, to'plam, dizayn, uslubiy yondashuv, samaradorlik, goniometriya, harorat.

ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЯ ФОРМЕННОЙ ОДЕЖДЫ С ЗАДАНЫМИ СВОЙСТВАМИ ДЛЯ ЖЕНЩИН ВОЕННОСЛУЖАЩИХ ДЛЯ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ УСЛОВИЙ

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Аннотация: В этой статье рассмотрено совершенствование методов проектирования и оценки эргономической рациональности конструкций одежды специального назначения с практической их отработкой и реализацией при создании новых образцов утепленной полевой одежды для женщин-военнослужащих.

Ключевые слова: Одежда, эргономическое качество, динамический, комплект, конструкция, методический подход, эффективность, гониометрия, температура.

Military uniforms are an important attribute that determines the combat capability of troops. Field uniforms are the basis of military personnel's combat equipment. In modern conditions, the role of military equipment has increased significantly. The purposeful introduction of innovative scientific developments and technologies into the production of military uniforms has significantly improved its consumer characteristics and transformed it from specialized clothing into one of the elements of the general combat equipment system of a modern soldier, which has a number of new (improved) properties that provide protection from both adverse climatic conditions and various damaging factors.

The development and improvement of the quality of military uniforms is inextricably linked with the degree of implementation of the latest technologies in the enterprises of the domestic light industry. In this area, innovations related to fabric manufacturing are the most important area. The developments are carried out in two directions: coloristic and intellectual. The coloristic direction is associated with the development of fundamentally new types of army camouflage with unusual color effects. [1]

As the current samples of military clothing from the standpoint of ergonomics, the characteristic of ergonomic quality indicators is given, classification and analysis of methods of their measurement and evaluation are carried out. The direction of improvement of methods for measuring and evaluating ergonomic indicators of dynamic compliance of the "human clothing" system has been determined. [2]

To achieve this goal, the following scientific and technical tasks were solved:

- 1) examination of ready-made samples of service clothes in order to identify their functional and ergonomic disadvantages and determine the range of parameters that affect the dynamic compliance of clothing with the conditions of service and combat activities;
- 2) investigation of the relationship between the biomechanical parameters of human movements in the main joints and the spatial arrangement of clothing segments;
- 3) development of methodological recommendations for constructing clothing designs with a given level of dynamic anthropometric conformity (for shoulder clothing - by forming its three-dimensional design solution in a three-dimensional automated clothing design system; for waist clothing - based on procedures for planar modification of the initial patterns of parts);

In terms of functional and dynamic characteristics, there are various options for sets of military clothing. The minimum required set of these characteristics has been determined, providing a sufficient degree of informativeness for the development of ergonomically rational structures. [3]

The factors describing the convenience of a set of clothes as a whole (convenience of putting on and taking off clothes) and general factors describing the ability of military personnel to perform their professional duties while wearing this set of clothes have the greatest impact on the assessment of military personnel of serial sets of clothes.;

The most significant influence (about 90%), in terms of limiting joint movements, is exerted by factors characterizing movements in the area of the sleeve-armhole knot and in the area of the middle seam of trousers. These design areas were selected as objects for further work to ensure the dynamic compliance of the "man-clothes" system. In a methodological approach to clothing design, which

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consists in a differentiated consideration of isolated movements in large joints and the use of biomechanical parameters as input data for constructing clothing designs with a given level of dynamic compliance. An analysis of the principle of shaping the design of clothing has been carried out, angular indicators affecting the spatial arrangement of structural parts have been systematized, and their optimal values have been determined. The application of this methodological approach makes it possible to ensure the required level of dynamic compliance of the product with extreme labor movements with satisfactory static compliance. [4]

Goniometry. The amplitudes of the maximum possible active movements in the large joints of the clothed tester were determined as criteria for assessing the dynamic compliance of the developed set of insulated clothing in comparison with the current equipment of female servicemen. A goniometer with a telescopic rod and a conventional protractor were used to measure the amplitudes of movements.

Assessment of thermal imaging efficiency. Since the operation of the developed samples of military clothing is assumed, according to the terms of reference, in climatic conditions with low ambient temperature, one of the number of requirements for winter clothing sets is its high thermal protection properties, which consist of the total thermal resistance of the clothing package, the physical properties of individual materials included in the package, and the rationality of the design clothing solutions. [5]

Comprehensive assessment of dynamic compliance. The objectivity of the design decisions made for the dynamic conformity of clothing was assessed by calculated single and complex indicators. The biomechanical characteristics of the working movements (the required level of dynamic compliance) were selected as the basic indicators.

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